

ISic0727

I.Sicily inscription 0727

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

marble (?)

Object

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

Prag 2018-03-15

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

site of ancient forum, Syracuse

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---] tr(ibunicia) pot(estate)

2. [---][p]erpetuus Aug[ustus][---]

Apparatus

Text of Manganaro (1989), p. 181 no. 60

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492380

EDCS 32701115

Bibliography

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 372

Henzen, W., Zangemeister, K. F. W. 1872-1913. *Ephemeris epigraphica. Corporis inscriptionum Latinarum supplementum*, edita iussu Instituti archaeologici Romani. Berlin. At VIII 684

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 181 no.60 fig.64

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